

White Paper “ Towards a European Smart Destinations Strategy”

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Abbreviations table

D3HUB	Data Driven Destinations Hub – EU Competence Centre for data management in Smart Destinations project
DG	Directorate General
DMO	Destination Management Organisation
DTI	Destinos Turísticos Inteligentes – Smart tourism destinations
ERDF	European regional Development Funds
ETDS	European Tourism Data Space
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communication technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
SME	Small and medium size companies
STD	Smart Tourism Destination
UN	United Nations

1. Introduction

Tourism is a key driver of the EU economy, but the sector—dominated by micro, small, and medium enterprises—faces fragmentation, limited funding access, weak coordination, and rising challenges from climate change, costs, and global competition. To address this, the EU is preparing a new EU Strategy for Sustainable Tourism as a non-legislative roadmap to boost sustainability, competitiveness, innovation, and resilience. It will brand Europe as the world’s top sustainable destination, strengthen Destination Management Organisations (DMOs), and support MSMEs in the green and digital transition through peer-learning networks, tailored funding, and smart tourism solutions, while adapting measures to national and regional needs.

In preparation for this Strategy, in 2025 the European Commission has launched a public and a targeted consultation, collecting about 1000 replies providing input for priorities to be included in the future Strategy. This paper deep-dives particularly into one element of the consultation, which asked DMOs for ideas on how to best support them, at EU level, in becoming true smart destinations, and it is the base for the brainstorming workshop on the topic organised by Torino as the 2025 European Capital of Smart Tourism.

Building on Spain’s successful *Red de Destinos Turísticos Inteligentes (Red DTI)* and aligned with the success criteria for the European Capital and Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism competitions, this workshop provides an opportunities for highly performant DMOs – the winners and finalists of the Capital and Green Pioneer awards – to discuss and inform the European Commission about lessons learnt, ambitions and priorities which need to be included in the upcoming EU Strategy for smart tourism to become a reality across European DMOs.

2. Start of the Art : evolution of the Smart Destination concept and strategies

While tourism policy remains decentralized within the European Union—given that Member States retain substantial competencies—recognition of the sector's strategic importance has prompted initiatives such as the European Capital of Smart Tourism. Launched in 2019, this initiative awards cities that excel in key areas including sustainability, accessibility, digitalization, and cultural heritage and creativity. These focus areas closely align with Spain’s framework outlined in the UNE 178501 standard, which emphasizes governance, sustainability, accessibility, innovation, and technology.

The emergence of the 'Smart Tourism Destination' concept in Spain has been driven by the evolving trends within the tourism industry, coupled with the shifting needs and expectations of tourists. To maintain competitiveness, destinations are increasingly adopting strategies that integrate sustainability, innovation, and digital transformation—principles embedded in the internationally recognized UNE 178501 standard. This standard emphasizes that a Smart Tourism Destination (STD) is not merely characterized by the deployment of digital infrastructure; rather, it aspires to transform the entire territory into a Smart destination through sustainable and efficient management practices. The ultimate goal is to enhance the quality of life for residents, visitors, and stakeholders alike, fostering socio-economic development while preserving environmental integrity.

In defining a destination as smart, technology plays a pivotal role—not only in enhancing the experience for tourists and residents but also as a critical tool for data collection and analysis. This data-driven approach supports informed decision-making, allows for benchmarking progress across established axes, and ensures continuous improvement in the destination’s overall sustainability, competitiveness, and social cohesion.

2.1 Analysis of the Smart Destination definition

To explore the concept further, it is important to analyse some of the most relevant definitions of Smart Destination:

- Boes et al. , (2015)¹ Places that use available technological tools and techniques to enable demand and supply to co-create value, pleasure and experiences for the tourist and wealth, profits and benefits for organisations and destinations.
- Lamsfus et al., (2015)² A tourism destination is smart when it makes intensive use of the technology provided for a smart city, referring to: 1) enhancing the tourism experience of visitors by personalising and making them aware of the local and tourism services and products available to them at the destination and 2) empowering destination management organisations, local institutions and tourism businesses to make their decisions and take actions based on the data produced at the destination, collected, managed and processed through the technology infrastructure.
- Buhalis & Maranggana (2013)³ Destinations should interconnect multiple stakeholders through a dynamic ICT-mediated platform in order to support the rapid exchange of information on tourism activities through machine-to-machine learning algorithm, which could improve their decision-making process, thus bringing intelligence to destinations.
- UNE 178501 Standard for STDs "An innovative area for tourism, accessible to everybody, consolidated on the basis of cutting-edge technological infrastructure that guarantees the sustainable development of a specific territory, facilitates the interaction and integration of visitors with their surroundings and increases the quality of their experience while in the tourism destination, as well as the quality of life of the people living in the area.
- Organisations such as SEGITTUR defined the concept of Smart Tourism Destination as: "A Smart Tourism Destination is an innovative tourism destination, consolidated and based on cutting-edge technological infrastructure and the tourism territory itself. An area highly committed to environmental sustainability, culture and socio-economic progress, provided

¹ Boes, K., Buhalis, D., & Inversini, A. (2015). Conceptualising smart tourism destination dimensions. In *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism 2015: Proceedings of the International Conference in Lugano, Switzerland, February 3-6, 2015* (pp. 391-403). Springer International Publishing.

² Lamsfus, C., Martín, D., Alzua-Sorzabal, A., Torres-Manzanera, E. (2015). Smart Tourism Destinations: An Extended Conception of Smart Cities Focusing on Human Mobility. In: Tussyadiah, I., Inversini, A. (eds) *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism 2015*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14343-9_27

³ Buhalis, D., & Maranggana, A. (2013). Smart tourism destinations. In *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism 2014: Proceedings of the International Conference in Dublin, Ireland, January 21-24, 2014* (pp. 553-564). Springer International Publishing.

with a smart system that collects information in a procedural way, analyses, and understands events in real-time, making it easier for visitors to interact with their surroundings and for managers to make decisions, increasing their efficiency and substantially improving the quality of the experience".

As can be seen, all of the above definitions underline the importance of technology in order to consider a destination as a smart destination. And some of the definitions already include the concepts of information and data exchange, as well as the possibility of measuring progress.

The practical implementation of the Smart Destinations initiative, coupled with the broader digitization of society, has significantly amplified the importance and volume of data within the tourism sector. The focus has shifted from collecting isolated data points to harnessing large-scale datasets, paving the way for data sharing through innovative data spaces.

International research increasingly recognizes the critical role of data science technologies—such as big data, social media analytics, and artificial intelligence—in advancing the sustainability and resilience of smart destinations (Aguirre Montero & López-Sánchez, 2021). The integration of these technologies enables destinations to optimize resource management, enhance visitor experiences, and support sustainable development goals. For example, Gomis-López and González-Reverté (2020), along with Sustacha (2022), emphasize the necessity of aligning smart tourism narratives with overarching sustainability strategies, particularly in mature coastal destinations.

Furthermore, scholarly work by Perles Ribes (2019) introduces the concept of "Smart Sustainability," a synergistic model that fuses sustainability principles with smart city methodologies to foster more efficient and sustainable destination management. Across these studies, the centrality of technology—especially data-driven tools—in measuring, managing, and achieving sustainability objectives is evident.

Recent bibliometric analyses, such as Madeira (2023), reveal interconnected clusters encompassing smart tourism, sustainable tourism, innovation, and smart cities—all underscoring the intrinsic link between sustainability and smart destination development. Sarkar (2019) further discusses the nexus between technology and sustainability within urban tourism contexts, emphasizing facets like urban ecotourism, gastronomic tourism, and intelligent transportation systems. Girardi (2017) introduces the Smartainability methodology, which employs both

qualitative and quantitative indicators to evaluate how well smart cities align with Sustainable Development Goals.

In parallel, Montero (2021) explores the intersection of data science and smart destination management, highlighting the importance of advanced analytics in areas such as tourism marketing, mobility, accessibility, and sustainability initiatives. Abu-Rayash (2021) proposes a comprehensive model for assessing urban smartness and sustainability across domains including economic, environmental, social, and energy metrics. Collectively, these contributions reaffirm the crucial role of technology and data science in quantifying and enhancing sustainability outcomes in smart destinations.

Equally important is understanding how the concept of the smart destination addresses contemporary challenges, notably overtourism. Overtourism exerts significant pressure on destinations, impacting local communities and environments. Accurate measurement of this phenomenon is essential to inform effective policies, as perceptions alone can be misleading. Buitrago Esquinas (2021) advocates for systematic measurement through indicators, surveys, interviews, and digital tools, enabling a comprehensive assessment of tourism pressure. Krajíčková (2022) emphasizes the importance of spatial analysis—for example, defining tourist zones and calculating pressure indicators—to better understand and manage local impacts. Nilsson (2019) situates overtourism within urban contexts, stressing the need to address both localized conflicts and global environmental impacts.

These studies collectively underscore the multidimensional nature of overtourism and highlight the importance of accessing diverse data sources to accurately measure its impacts. Such data-driven approaches can be expanded and adapted to address other emergent challenges facing tourism destinations. This underscores the necessity of investing in advanced tools, indicators, and methodologies that harness data analytics to inform strategic decision-making, foster sustainable practices, and develop resilient, future-ready destinations.

The recent doctoral Thesis, “Tourism data spaces in smart tourism destinations: conceptual and methodological approach” (Ordóñez-Martínez, 2024) complements the previous research by adding a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the tourism data space on Smart Destinations.

3. What’s been done so far

Europe has been working for a while in the support to destinations towards their green and digital transition, some key projects already implemented or under implementation are:

- Sustainable Eu Tourism⁴
- Smart Tourism Destinations⁵
- D3HUB, EU Competence Centre for Data management in Smart Destinations⁶
- European Capital of Smart Tourism⁷

In all this four projects, it has been developed an important work to define the needs and requirements of DMOs, as well as to identify potential solutions to overcome challenges that DMOs are facing. All the work developed or still under development is ground for the definition of a methodology that will take into consideration the diversity and complexity of the tourism ecosystem and the great range of sizes and characteristics of the European destinations.

Some key findings of these projects are summarised as follows:

1. “Sustainable EU Tourism – Shaping the Tourism of Tomorrow”

A project running from December 2023 to December 2025, aligned with the EU’s Transition Pathway for Tourism. Its core aim is to support EU tourism destinations in developing greater sustainability and resilience, with balanced attention to economic, social, cultural and environmental dimensions.

Key actions include identifying challenges & best practices; establishing peer-to-peer twinning among destinations facing similar issues; informing DMOs (Destination Management Organisations) about support tools; and conducting communication campaigns.

The project has mapped 31 key challenges grouped under four dimensions: economic (e.g. overtourism, managing off-season, gentrification), environmental (climate impact, pollution,

⁴ https://transport.ec.europa.eu/tourism/transition-eu-tourism/sustainable-eu-tourism-shaping-tourism-tomorrow_en

⁵ <https://smarttourismdestinations.eu>

⁶ <https://www.d3hub-competencecentre.eu>

⁷ https://smart-tourism-capital.ec.europa.eu/index_en

habitat loss), socio-cultural (preserving identity, infrastructure strain, seasonal work), and governance (resource management, strategy, stakeholder coordination).

From an inventory of 272 case studies, 50 best-practice examples were selected for their replicability, innovation, data availability, and balanced coverage of destination types (urban, rural, islands, etc.). Examples include Bordeaux (accessible infrastructure), Florence (“Smart City Control Room” for tourism flow monitoring), Lower Saxony region (environmental engagement), Wilder Kaiser (social inclusion).

Survey Results from DMOs: Over 220 DMOs responded, across all EU member states. Many already have ongoing initiatives in place: about two-thirds are working on improving sustainability and resilience. The environmental, socio-cultural and economic dimensions are all being addressed.

Success Factors & Barriers:

- What helps: strong stakeholder engagement; political commitment; clear vision & strategy; securing funding; capacity building; open mindset.
- What holds back: lack of resources; limited political will in some places; low stakeholder cooperation; resistance or skepticism; insufficient prioritization of less glamorous yet essential areas (e.g. visitor flow management, crisis planning).

2. Smart Tourism Destinations

Its goal is to help EU urban tourism destinations make the transition to smart & sustainable management via better data systems. The main focus was on data mastering — i.e. collecting, managing, analysing and using data to inform decisions in tourism governance, visitor experience, marketing, and service delivery.

Major Outputs & Achievements: Development of a Smart Tourism Toolkit, structured around pillars such as strategy & governance, data collection & technological solutions. Webinars, workshops and coaching for destination managers have been delivered. Creation of a Digital Library of tools, case studies, resources to support replication and learning.

Selection (via Call for Expression of Interest) of about 50 destination managers who were participating in tailored journeys to adopt data-driven tools and practices.

Challenges & Insights

- Many destinations are quite early in their data maturity: investments in infrastructure, technical skills, data governance are uneven.
- Data use is often reactive rather than proactive (marketing, monitoring, crisis response vs long-term strategy).
- Need for clear business cases and evidence of ROI to convince local authorities and SMEs to invest.

3. D3HUB Competence Centre (Tourism “of Tomorrow” – Data-Driven Destinations Hub)

D3HUB is an EU-funded initiative designed to create a European Competence Centre for data-driven tourism destinations.

It supports Destination Management Organisations (DMOs) and tourism SMEs in their green and digital transition, with a focus on turning data into actionable insights for smarter governance and visitor management.

After an open call, 40 DMOs have been selected which represents a balanced geographical representation as well as different administrative levels (local, regional, national) and sizes of destinations as well as typologies of tourism.

The 40 DMOs have been grouped around 4 main data-driven clusters:

- Redistributing tourist flows in space and time
- Managing the balance between residents, visitors, and stakeholders
- Climate change mitigation and adaptation
- Supporting emerging destinations to attract quality and sustainable tourism

Many destinations struggle to collect, manage, and analyse tourism data effectively. D3HUB provides ready-made tools, guidelines, and expertise so destinations can understand visitor flows, monitor impacts, and make informed decisions.

The tourism sector must adapt to the EU's climate and digital agendas. D3HUB helps destinations apply digital technologies (data platforms, smart monitoring) and integrate sustainability indicators (environmental impact, resident satisfaction, accessibility).

Smaller DMOs and tourism businesses often lack staff or technical skills to use advanced tools. D3HUB acts as a Competence Centre, offering training, tailored support, and peer learning opportunities to strengthen local capabilities.

Data-driven strategies allow destinations to adapt offers, improve services, and diversify tourism products. Better insights lead to higher-quality, more personalised, and more sustainable visitor experiences.

D3HUB fosters multi-stakeholder governance. This ensures that tourism growth is balanced with local needs and long-term resilience.

4. European Capital & Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism

An EU competition / initiative to recognize cities for excellence in smart, sustainable, and accessible tourism.

Two related awards: European Capital of Smart Tourism (for larger cities, >100,000 population) and European Green Pioneer (for smaller ones, 25,000-100,000, with particular emphasis on green transition, sustainability)

The process of engaging with the competition provided diverse learning opportunities for cities:⁸

- **Internal Audit and Stocktaking:** For many, preparing the application served as a crucial opportunity to **consolidate existing initiatives and articulate their narrative** as a smart tourism destination. This process helped cities **discover and document** what they were already doing well across various areas such as sustainability, accessibility, and digitalisation. It often led to increased internal awareness among city departments and stakeholders about their collective achievements.
- **Identifying Strengths and Weaknesses:** The application process forced cities to reflect on their performance against specified criteria, helping them to pinpoint areas of strength

⁸ Quoting X. Font and L. A. Pace, *Internal Evaluation of the Smart Tourism Capital Initiative and Green Pioneer Programme*, July 2025

and areas needing improvement. For instance, one city identified accessibility as its most challenging area. Another noted a lack of sufficient receptive structures compared to tourist flows.

- **Catalyst for New Strategies and Initiatives:** Participation could act as an **incentive for future improvements**. One winning entity explicitly stated that their failures in initial applications were "invaluable lessons" that highlighted the need for a comprehensive tourism strategy, which ultimately contributed to their later win. Another city found that the work initiated for the competition indirectly led to new projects focused on sustainable tourism.
- **Developing Skills and Confidence:** The process, especially preparing for the defence in front of the jury, pushed some cities to hone their communication and presentation skills. One winning city, a first-time participant, gained significant confidence and sought professional help to improve their presentation skills, demonstrating how the challenge can foster growth.
- **Importance of Collaboration:** Many cities emphasized that **collaboration, both internal and external**, was crucial for preparing a strong application. For some, working with diverse stakeholders was already part of their daily operations. For others, the competition served as a "golden opportunity" to foster public-private partnerships for the first time. One winning city significantly developed its internal and external working groups for tourism development after its win.

From the previous projects, the main challenges have been identified:

1. **Resource Constraints**

- Limited financial, technical, and human resources, especially in small or rural destinations.
- Dependence on short-term EU project funding without continuity.

2. **Uneven Readiness**

- Wide disparities in digital infrastructure, data literacy, and governance maturity across regions.
- Some destinations still at an early stage of smart tourism adoption.

3. **Governance Complexity**

- Difficult coordination among multiple stakeholders with competing priorities.
- Lack of clarity in roles, responsibilities, and accountability.

4. **Resistance to Change**

- Political hesitation, skepticism, or inertia from stakeholders who prefer traditional models.
- Low prioritisation of less “visible” measures like visitor flow monitoring or crisis planning.

5. **Balancing Growth and Sustainability**

- Tension between the drive for visitor growth and the need to manage overtourism, gentrification, and environmental pressures.
- Ensuring benefits are equitably distributed to residents.

6. **Data Gaps & Fragmentation**

- Inconsistent standards and methodologies for collecting and sharing data.
- Fragmentation of datasets, limited interoperability, and concerns about privacy.

7. **Climate & Environmental Risks**

- Destinations increasingly exposed to climate change impacts.
- Difficulty in aligning tourism strategies with broader EU climate neutrality goals.

3.1 Comparing Segittur’s Smart Destinations Strategy and European Capital of Smart Tourism pillars

Spain, through the Segittur, entity depending on the Spanish Ministry of Tourism, has been the first Member State in developing an integrated Smart Destinations Strategy that includes a methodology, indicators, the creation of a network and it is supported by standards (UNE 178 and ff). The key axes of the Strategy are the following ones:

- **Innovation:** Fostering a culture of innovation and technological adoption within the destination.
- **Technology:** Implementing and utilizing technology to improve tourism management and enhance the visitor experience.
- **Sustainability:** Promoting environmentally, socially, and economically sustainable tourism practices.
- **Accessibility:** Ensuring that the destination is accessible to all visitors, regardless of their abilities.
- **Governance:** Establishing effective governance structures and collaborative partnerships to manage the DTI initiative.

Apart of this 5 axes, the strategy puts a big emphasis on marketing & promotion in order to showcase the destination's smart tourism offerings.

European Capital of Smart Tourism - Key Axes:

- **Accessibility:** Making the destination easily accessible to everyone, regardless of age, ability, or background.
- **Sustainability:** Minimizing the environmental impact of tourism and promoting responsible travel practices.
- **Digitalisation:** Embracing digital technologies to enhance the visitor experience, improve tourism management, and promote the destination.
- **Cultural Heritage & Creativity:** Showcasing the destination's unique cultural heritage and fostering creativity through tourism initiatives.

Feature	SEGITTUR's DTI Strategy (General)	European Capital of Smart Tourism
Core Focus	Transforming destinations into smart, sustainable, and accessible places.	Recognizing and promoting destinations that excel in smart tourism practices.
Accessibility	A key pillar, focusing on inclusive tourism for all.	A core axis, emphasizing ease of access for all visitors.
Sustainability	A key pillar, emphasizing responsible tourism practices.	A core axis, focusing on minimizing environmental impact.
Digitalisation /Technology	A key pillar, focusing on using tech.	A core axis, focusing on using tech.
Innovation	A key pillar, fostering a culture of creativity and new solutions.	Contained in Cultural Heritage and Creativity.

Feature	SEGITTUR's DTI Strategy (General)	European Capital of Smart Tourism
Governance	A key pillar, emphasizing collaborative management.	Implied through the award criteria, needing strategies to accomplish goals.
Marketing & Promotion	A key pillar, showcasing the destination's smart tourism offerings.	Indirectly addressed, as successful initiatives often require effective promotion.

Key Differences & Similarities:

- Similarities: Both frameworks share a strong emphasis on accessibility, sustainability, and digitalization as core components of smart tourism.
- Differences: SEGITTUR's DTI strategy places more explicit emphasis on governance as a critical enabler for success. The European Capital of Smart Tourism explicitly highlights the importance of cultural heritage and creativity.

The comparison shows that the Spanish model offers a methodological and governance framework, while the EU initiative provides visibility and recognition. A European Smart Destinations Strategy could integrate both approaches—combining structured transformation with incentives and recognition to accelerate adoption across Member States.

4. Vision for European smart destinations

Despite the different efforts at Member State and EU level, the current landscape presents the following challenges:

- **Heterogeneous Digital Maturity:** Varying levels of technological adoption hinder seamless interoperability and data sharing, while disparities in digital infrastructure and skills among different regions and communities are needed to promote inclusive smart tourism. This challenge generates a digital divide and accessibility challenge
- **Limited Data Ecosystem:** Fragmented and siloed data sources impede comprehensive analysis and strategic insights. Which includes Data Governance and challenges addressed to ensuring compliance with GDPR and ethical data handling standards
- **Sustainable Tourism Management:** Balancing technological innovations with environmental conservation, social equity, and cultural preservation.
- **Overtourism and Carrying Capacity:** Navigating the balance between tourism growth and environmental/local preservation. Measuring and mitigating the negative impacts of excessive visitor numbers on local communities and ecosystems.
- **Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving residents, local businesses, and other stakeholders in the planning and implementation of smart destination strategies, including overcoming institutional and technological barriers to data sharing and joint innovation
- **Funding and Investment:** Securing adequate resources and funding for technological infrastructure, innovation projects, and capacity building.
- **Maintaining Authentic Cultural Identity:** Using technology to enhance cultural heritage without compromising authenticity or leading to commodification.
- **Innovation Adoption and Change Management:** Overcoming resistance to technological change and ensuring that stakeholders are adequately trained and engaged.
- **Alignment with Policy and Regulatory Frameworks:** Navigating complex EU, national, and regional policies that may influence or restrict certain smart destination initiatives.
- **Measuring and Monitoring Impact:** Developing reliable indicators and frameworks to assess progress, sustainability, and overall success.

- **Scalability and Replicability:** Ensuring that successful smart tourism solutions can be scaled or adapted across diverse destinations with varying characteristics.

Addressing these challenges requires more than technology. It calls for shared governance, citizen engagement, and coordinated investment across the EU. By integrating sustainability, inclusivity, and digital innovation into a common European framework, destinations can deliver better services for visitors, higher quality of life for residents, and stronger resilience for local economies.

4.1 Strategic pillars for development

In the pursuit of sustainable and competitive European destinations, a holistic approach grounded in innovation, sustainability, inclusivity, and resilience is essential. This framework is structured around four strategic key pillars that collectively guide the transformation of destinations into truly smart and resilient places.

a. Digital & Data-Driven transformation in line with the Tourism Transition Pathway

- Implementing data-informed policies, operational efficiency, and personalized offerings
- Promoting capacity building for data literacy among stakeholders
- Establishing open and interoperable data ecosystems via the European Tourism Data Space, ensuring secure data exchange

b. Sustainability, Resource Optimization, and Cultural Preservation

- Using IoT, AI, and digital monitoring to optimize energy, water, and waste management
- Applying data analytics to manage tourist flows, reduce overtourism, and enhance visitor distribution
- Ensuring digital solutions respect cultural and ecological integrity

c. Inclusivity, Accessibility, and Participatory Governance

- Deploying accessible digital services, multilingual interfaces, and citizen participation portals
- Facilitating data transparency and co-creation processes involving residents and visitors
- Leveraging the European Tourism Data Space to foster inclusive data access

d. Resilience and Crisis Management Enabled by Data Ecosystems

- Developing real-time monitoring systems for safety, health, and environmental crises
- Building adaptive infrastructure supported by interoperable data streams through the European Tourism Data Space

4.2 Setting up a European Tourism Agency

Establishing a European Tourism Agency would be a strategic move with significant benefits for the EU tourism sector. Such an agency would serve as a centralized body dedicated to coordinating, supporting, and promoting sustainable and innovative tourism across EU Member States.

Firstly, a European Tourism Agency would facilitate greater alignment of policies and practices, ensuring a cohesive approach to addressing common challenges such as overtourism, environmental sustainability, and digital transformation. It would enable the sharing of best practices, data, and innovation, fostering a more resilient and competitive tourism industry.

Secondly, it would enhance cooperation and coordination among destinations, helping to improve branding and marketing at the European level, thereby attracting more international visitors and promoting less-visited regions. This promotes the balanced distribution of tourism flows and reduces pressure on overburdened sites. This task will be implemented in coordination with existing entities

Thirdly, a dedicated agency would support the development of a unified digital ecosystem, encouraging interoperability and the sharing of data and technological solutions—crucial for building smart destinations and delivering personalized, high-quality visitor experiences. The Agency could become the Governance Authority for the European Tourism Data Space, ensuring the smooth deployment at all levels and cross-sector.

Finally, it would serve as a voice for tourism within European policy frameworks, advocating for investments, funding, and policy measures that support long-term sustainability, accessibility, and inclusivity. In this case, avoiding overlapping and duplication in the implementation of projects and initiatives and ensuring a good coordination of all funds related directly or indirectly to tourism.

Within the activities to be implemented by the European Tourism Agency, the following would be included:

- Setting up, defining and implementing the European Smart Destinations Strategy
- Coordinating and harmonizing policies and initiatives among Member States.
- Developing and promoting standards and best practices for digital and sustainable tourism, working together with entities as ISO or ITU
- Managing and overseeing the European Tourism Data Space to enable cross-border data interoperability.
- Providing support for project funding, capacity building, and innovation, ensuring the alignment of all funding lines related to tourism (independently from the DG in charge of the funds)
- Integrating the EU Competence Centre
- Acting as a facilitator and mediator among stakeholders—public authorities, private sector, academia, and civil society.

4.3 Setting up a European Tourism Academy

The European Tourism Academy should primarily be affiliated with DG MOVE; however, in the future, it should operate independently under the European Tourism Agency. The foundations of the European Tourism Academy must be based on lessons learned from projects such as D3HUB – EU Competence Centre and FACILITATE, as well as other initiatives like Interreg, COSME and Erasmus Plus.

The Academy should be coordinated with various universities across Europe, but the most important aspect is to develop a shared academic programme that guides the creation and development of Smart Tourist Destinations, based on the European Strategy of Smart Destinations. The principal beneficiaries of the European Tourism Academy should be:

- firstly, the **destinations** themselves, along with their workers, officials, and representatives – including the political level. This encompasses not only those directly responsible for tourism policies but also those involved in sustainable tourism development and other departments that are directly or indirectly related to the creation of Smart Tourist Destinations.

- The concept of a Smart Tourist Destination has been conceived as a comprehensive, global framework that encompasses all departments within a destination. When referring to destinations, we include all types—whether local, regional, or national—regardless of their territorial scope.
- The next group of beneficiaries includes **companies**. We must develop a significant number of firms trained in the methodology of Smart Tourist Destinations, capable of contributing to refining and implementing this methodology in a harmonised and standardised manner across all European destinations, regardless of the country in which they are located. These companies should also assist in creating a large workforce equipped with a shared knowledge base, enabling the measurement of progress during the transition to Smart Destinations.
- Companies with this expertise will be responsible for helping establish governance at destination level, implementing strategies, and defining municipal plans aligned with the European methodology for Smart Tourist Destinations. They will carry out the various actions and initiatives outlined in the action plan.
- Finally, the third group of beneficiaries consists of students. It is essential to explore how cooperation with universities across Europe can prepare future European leaders—both political and business—and future workforce members to implement the policies and strategies for Smart Tourist Destinations.

Collaboration with universities should involve establishing partnerships, joint training programmes, and shared curricula. The European Academy will play a crucial role in coordinating and validating these educational programmes to ensure all participating universities deliver training based on the same methodology and knowledge, regardless of location.

The goal is to prepare future leaders, workers, and innovators who will implement these strategies, thereby positioning Europe as a world-leading Smart Tourist Destination. The methodology should not only facilitate implementation but also support ongoing measurement of progress (a common European set of sustainable tourism indicators), ensuring that all destinations advance uniformly in this transition towards intelligent tourism

4.4 Collaboration and co-creation with key actors

The development of an effective and sustainable European Tourism Strategy requires a multi-stakeholder approach, involving a diverse range of entities and institutions. These organisations bring critical expertise, resources, and perspectives necessary to shape policies, foster innovation, and ensure the transition towards smart, resilient, and sustainable tourism destinations across Europe. This report outlines the key entities and institutions that should be actively engaged in this strategic process.

1. European Union Institutions and agencies

- European Commission, apart from DG MOVE, other departments managing key programmes (DG Regio, DG Connect...) and Agencies as HADEA, EISMEA...
- European Parliament
- Committee of the Regions
- JRC (managing the EU Tourism Dashboard)
- Eurostat (to support the definition of the indicators)

2. National Governments and Agencies

- National Tourism Boards and Ministries: Responsible for implementing the strategy at the national level, coordinating cross-sectoral policy, and facilitating public-private partnerships.
- Ministries of Environment, Culture, and Innovation: Since not all Member States have Tourism departments and agencies and to ensure alignment with sustainability, cultural preservation, and technological advancement objectives.
- Regional and Local Authorities: As key players in on-the-ground implementation, they manage local policies, infrastructure, and community engagement.

3. National Research & Innovation Bodies

- Universities and Academic Institutions: To provide expertise, develop educational programmes, and pilot innovative smart destination solutions.
- Innovation Hubs and Technology Clusters: Facilitating digital transformation, smart technologies, and pilot projects at regional and local levels.

4. Industry and Private Sector Entities

- Tourism Associations and lobbies (e.g., European Travel Commission, NECSTouR, CityDNA, ETOA, EU Travel Tech...): To represent industry and DMOs interests, promote sustainable tourism, and facilitate stakeholder collaboration.
- Hotels, Hospitality, and Transport Companies: Implementing innovative practices aligned with smart destination principles.
- Tech Companies and Start-ups: Developing digital solutions, data analytics, and IoT applications to enhance tourist experiences and destination management.

5. International Organisations

- World Tourism Organization (UN Tourism): To align the European strategy with global best practices and promote international cooperation.
- OECD

6. Entities coordinating key EU projects and initiatives: due to their in deep knowledge on trends and requirements affecting the tourism sector

7. Other entities representing the civil society and sustainability

5. Implementation framework

5.1 Learning from the Spanish Smart Destinations Strategy

The Spanish methodology, developed by SEGITTUR⁹, offers valuable lessons for Europe. Its phased model demonstrates how destinations can progress through structured steps: initial diagnosis, action planning, implementation, and continuous monitoring. By using standardized requirements and indicators, Spain has created a system that ensures comparability and fosters continuous improvement across its network (Red DTI).

For the EU, the main takeaway is the importance of structured transformation, common indicators, and cyclical monitoring—principles that can be adapted at European scale without replicating national detail.

5.2 Building on the European Smart Destinations Strategy

Based on the Spanish Smart Destinations Strategy experience, and the learnings from key projects as D3HUB-EU Competence Centre and DEPLOYTOUR, as well as key projects contributing to the digital and green transition of cities as the Intelligent Cities Challenges, the European Tourism Strategy of Smart Destinations, could follow the next steps:

- **Co-creation work to agree on the overall strategy.** Working with the ecosystem to agree on the methodological approach, the definition of the indicators and requirements for the EU Strategy. This work can be done, by generating working groups and an European Consultation, and then worked with key experts. The idea is to establish a Common Vision and Framework, in which it will be defined the overarching objectives aligned with EU policies such as the Green Deal, European Digital Strategy, and Tourism Transition Pathway; it will be developed a shared conceptual framework adaptable to diverse regional contexts; and it will be agreed benchmarks for maturity levels and sustainability metrics.

⁹ Segittur Methodology: https://www.destinosinteligentes.es/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Manual-Gestion-Metodologia-DTI_Junio-2024.pdf

- **Development of a Smart Destination Readiness tool:** this tool will be compulsory for all destinations at EU level to define their maturity as a smart and sustainable destination.
- **Definition of a set of Smart and Sustainable Tourism indicators,** based on the work done by D3HUB, and working together with Eurostat and the JRC. This set of indicators have to be approved at EU level and if possible, together with UN Tourism. It will be important to generate a clear standardisation and common measurement all over Europe and beyond
- **Define the templates of the procedures to be followed:** definition of the template of the Action Plan, definition of procedures to generate the European Network of Smart Destinations, etc
- **Promote Interoperability and Data Ecosystems:** Develop consistent **standards and protocols** based on **ISO/ITU norms** for data sharing and privacy, aligned with the European Tourism Data Space
- **Engage Stakeholders and Build Capacity:** Create multi-stakeholder forums involving authorities, private sector, civil society, and tourists. Launch transnational training programs on digital literacy, data management, and sustainability. Facilitate knowledge exchange through pilot projects, case studies, and peer learning.
- **Develop comprehensive training programs** tailored for local authorities, industry actors, and communities focusing on digital literacy, data management, sustainable practices, and the use of new technologies. Linked with the learnings of the FACILITATE project, Pact for Skills and other initiatives.
- **Secure Funding and Investment:** ensuring the access to funds for all destinations, and coordinating the existing funds (ERDF, HE, Interreg...) re-addressing them to cover the actions defined by the Action Plans
- **Monitoring, Evaluation, and Refinement:** this includes the definition of KPIs relating to sustainability, digital maturity, stakeholder engagement, and visitor satisfaction. Aligned with the EU Tourism Dashboard and the EU Competence Centre include real-time tracking of progress.
- **Expand and Sustain the Network:** Establish a **European Network of Smart Destinations** to facilitate ongoing collaboration and knowledge sharing. Encourage member states to integrate the **European Smart Destination Framework** into national and regional strategic plans. Develop **regulatory frameworks** that facilitate data sharing, public-private partnerships, and innovation hubs.

- **Consolidate and Expand the European Network of Smart Destinations:** Formalize a **European Network of Smart Destinations** coordinated by the **European Tourism Agency** to facilitate peer learning, joint initiatives, and co-marketing. Promote cross-border tourism experiences, integrated mobility, and synchronized digital services to attract larger markets. Support continuous innovation by connecting with European research and innovation hubs, technological companies, and start-ups.

Under the leadership of DG MOVE—currently and in the future through the European Tourism Agency—a comprehensive and strategic program will be developed to shape Europe's smart destinations ecosystem. Building on insights and best practices from successful international initiatives, DG MOVE's role will be to provide overarching leadership and coordination for the entire strategy.

The process will be characterized by multiple engagement points to ensure active participation of the ecosystem stakeholders:

- **Strategic Framework and Methodology Development:** Collaborating with key stakeholders and organizing a public consultation to co-create a robust strategy that reflects diverse perspectives and needs.
- **Indicators Definition and Monitoring:** Working closely with entities such as Eurostat, JRC, UN Tourism, OECD, and the EU Competence Centre to establish meaningful indicators that measure progress and impact.
- **Strategy Implementation:** To ensure broad outreach across European destinations and foster a thriving smart destinations economy, DG MOVE will introduce a validation program. This initiative will certify companies offering innovative services aligned with destination development goals. This is specially important to ensure that all destinations receive standardised services and follow the European Smart Destinations Strategy, while generating an ecosystem of companies (mostly SMEs) all over Europe that will work directly with the destinations helping them to implement the strategy and to gather data to measure the indicators. Europe will generate a business ecosystem that will be ready, with a real experience on the ground, to export the methodology internationally.
- **Dashboard and Performance Measurement:** Developing a comprehensive dashboard integrating data from the Smart Destinations Readiness tool and the data gathered at destination's level to measure the indicators. This platform will be

interconnected with the EU Tourism Dashboard and the EU Competence Centre to enable real-time monitoring and strategic decision-making. This action will be particularly important to ensure that data is gathered at destination level. This will help not only to the destinations, that will improve their decision-making mechanisms with accurate and quality data, but it will also deeply enrich the data that entities as Eurostat and JRC need for their statistics and research. Finally, this data, managed in a proper way and following the European Tourism Data Space indications, it will contribute to generate a data market at local, regional, national and European level, contributing to support a new data economy for the business ecosystem, taking into consideration specially the SMEs.

This progressive approach aims to position Europe as a leader in smart tourism, fostering innovation, sustainability, and competitive advantage across its diverse destinations.

Once the European Smart Destination Strategy is finalized, a structured and transparent process will be established to ensure effective implementation and ongoing evolution. This process will be rooted in a continuous improvement framework, promoting iterative development and adaptability across destinations.

Key elements of this process will include:

- **Regular Validation and Evaluation:** Destinations will undergo a comprehensive assessment every two years to validate their progress, measure improvements, and identify areas for further development. This cyclical evaluation will ensure that strategies

remain relevant, innovative, and aligned with evolving industry standards and technological advancements.

- **Participatory Feedback Loops:** Continuous engagement with destination stakeholders, local communities, and industry players will be essential to refine initiatives, address challenges, and leverage emerging opportunities.
- **Incentives and Qualification Criteria:** To motivate active participation and reward excellence, the program could incorporate various incentives. These may include preferential eligibility for targeted funding opportunities, increased access to co-financing or grants, and eligibility for special recognition or certification. Criteria for participation might prioritize destinations demonstrating tangible progress, innovation capacity, and commitment to sustainability and inclusivity.
- **Transparency and Recognition:** Destinations that meet or exceed benchmarks will be publicly recognized, fostering healthy competition and encouraging the dissemination of best practices (this should be aligned with the European Capital of Smart Destinations Award). This recognition can serve as a catalyst for continuous improvement and inspire other destinations to elevate their smart tourism initiatives.
- **Adaptive Funding and Support Mechanisms:** Based on the progress assessments, tailored support, capacity-building initiatives, and funding adjustments can be provided, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently and effectively to foster sustainable growth and innovation in Europe's smart destinations.

Overall, this structured, cyclical process aims to create a dynamic ecosystem where destinations are continuously evolving, learning from each other, and achieving excellence in delivering smart, sustainable, and competitive tourism experiences across Europe.

5.3 Risks and mitigation

The transition towards smart destinations, while promising, also presents several risks that must be openly acknowledged and carefully managed. Addressing these risks upfront is essential to guarantee credibility and to ensure that the strategy delivers balanced and sustainable outcomes across Europe.

One of the main risks is the persistence of the digital divide. Certain territories, particularly rural and less developed regions, may struggle to keep pace with more advanced destinations. Without corrective action, this imbalance could deepen existing inequalities within the European tourism ecosystem. To counter this, the strategy foresees targeted support, both financial and technical, to ensure that no region is left behind.

Another challenge relates to data privacy and ethics. The expansion of data-driven decision-making in tourism requires strict compliance with GDPR and the responsible use of artificial intelligence. To safeguard citizens’ trust, the European Tourism Data Space must be governed with robust standards that guarantee transparency, accountability, and ethical oversight in all data-related processes.

There is also the risk of overreliance on external technology providers. If European destinations depend heavily on global players outside the EU, Europe could lose digital sovereignty in a sector

that is strategically important for its economy and cultural identity. Promoting European providers, ensuring interoperability, and investing in open standards are crucial measures to mitigate this dependency.

Finally, digitalization itself has an environmental footprint. Data centres, IoT infrastructure, and other digital tools consume energy and resources, which may inadvertently undermine sustainability objectives. To address this, the strategy calls for green ICT standards, the integration of renewable energy solutions, and systematic monitoring of environmental performance.

5.4 Economic impact and investment priorities

Smart destinations must be understood not only as a policy ambition but also as a strategic investment for Europe’s long-term competitiveness. By modernising the tourism ecosystem through digital transformation, sustainability, and inclusivity, the strategy will generate significant economic and social returns.

At the economic level, smart destinations will strengthen Europe’s competitive position in global tourism markets, making destinations more attractive, efficient, and resilient. The strategy will create new employment opportunities, not only in the tourism sector itself but also in related industries such as digital services, environmental technologies, and cultural innovation. A particularly important dimension is the role of SMEs and start-ups, which are expected to become key drivers of innovation and service provision. Their involvement will foster a dynamic business ecosystem capable of scaling solutions across Europe and exporting them internationally.

Investments will be required in several areas, including digital infrastructure at local and regional level, the creation of interoperable data systems, and training initiatives developed through the European Tourism Academy. Equally important will be dedicated support for SMEs and start-ups, enabling them to refine and deploy smart tourism solutions. In parallel, substantial resources will be needed to implement and expand the European Tourism Data Space, which forms the backbone of data-driven decision-making across destinations.

The financial architecture for this transformation should combine existing instruments—such as the European Regional Development Fund, Horizon Europe, InvestEU, Interreg, and COSME—with more targeted mechanisms. To ensure coherence, efficiency, and visibility, the strategy recommends establishing a dedicated funding stream for Smart Destinations, coordinated by the future European Tourism Agency. Such a mechanism would align diverse sources of financing, avoid duplication, and create strong incentives for destinations to actively participate in the transformation.

6. Conclusions

The European Strategy of Smart Destinations aims to transform tourism across Europe by leveraging digital innovation, sustainable practices, and active community engagement. In the short term, the strategy focuses on modernizing infrastructure, enhancing digital services, and establishing a common framework for measuring progress. In the long term, its objectives include ensuring sustainable growth, improving climate resilience, fostering innovation, and strengthening the global reputation of European destinations.

This strategy does not depart from scratch, having as a baseline the Tourism Transition Pathway, but also key projects as the EU Competence Centre, and the European Tourism Data Space, as well as other initiatives as the EU Tourism Dashboard.

A key element of this strategy is the development of a standardized European methodology and a common set of indicators. This ensures consistency in how destinations are assessed and enables reliable benchmarking across regions. Such standardization facilitates the sharing of best practices, more effective policy-making, and transparent monitoring of progress towards strategic goals. It also helps attract investments by providing clear and comparable data on destination performance, sustainability, and visitor satisfaction.

The implementation of a unified approach through a common methodology and indicators promotes coherence among diverse destinations, enabling tailored yet aligned strategies that contribute to overall European competitiveness. The involvement of SMEs in key parts of the process will be key to ensure a smart destinations economy in which the SMEs will have a key role in supporting the implementation of the strategy, while improving their services offer and allowing them to export them out of Europe.

Furthermore, the creation of the European Tourism Agency will act as a central governing body to coordinate efforts, support innovation, advocate for sustainable practices, and promote collaboration among Member States. This agency will ensure that strategic initiatives are effectively executed, funding is efficiently allocated, and progress is transparently communicated.

The European Strategy of Smart Destinations endeavours to position the EU tourism sector as resilient, innovative, and sustainable. By combining digital transformation with standardized

assessment tools, the strategy aims to foster long-term economic, environmental, and social benefits for local communities and stakeholders alike, ensuring Europe remains a leading global tourist destination well into the future, while increasing the quality of life of their citizens.

Annex I Questions for discussion for the meeting to be organised in Torino on December 2nd, 2025

Torino Is the European Capital of Smart Tourism 2025, in this framework, the European Commission has organised a workshop with winners and finalists of this Award, in order to start generating a common agreement of an European framework to support and boost European Smart Destinations.

Based on the White Paper, these questions were the ground of discussion to work with the DMOs:

- 1. Section 2 of this paper sums up the lessons learnt from a number of ongoing and past EU projects which all aim at supporting DMOs in developing smarter and more sustainable practices. Would you say the findings are complete? If not, based on your experience, what does a DMO need from the EU to become a smart destination?**
- 2. Is there a framework, at regional, national, or international level, which you use and are part of, which you think we should consider as a good model for a EU framework of smart tourism?**
- 3. About the methodology to build a EU framework – which elements, or pillars, would you absolutely need? Is the Spanish example a good one? Or the framework set up by the European Capital and Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism competitions?**
- 4. About implementing this EU framework, if we had one: what would work for you, as a DMO? How do we avoid burdening you in an effort to help?**
- 5. How should we go about measuring and monitoring your performance as a smart destination, and/or the success of this EU framework, in your opinion?**